

Deliverable D 9.3 Data Management Plan (DMP)

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1. Executive Summary

The OPEUS project participates in the H2020 pilot action on open access to research data. The aim of OPEUS is to develop a simulation methodology and accompanying modelling tool to evaluate, improve and optimise the energy consumption of rail systems, with a particular focus on in-vehicle innovation. To fulfil its objectives and achieve its aim, OPEUS needs to access, collect, create, process and manage various data types.

This is deliverable report D9.3 “Data Management Plan” (DMP) for the OPEUS project, providing an analysis of the main elements of the data management methodology that will be used with regard to data sets to be used by the project throughout its lifetime. In particular, the report outlines:

- how the research data will be handled during and after the project
- the types of data that to be collected and/or generated and processed
- the methodologies and standards to be followed
- whether/how the data may be shared
- how the data will be curated and preserved.

Following the “EC Guidelines for Data Management in Horizon 2020”¹, the document first presents its purpose and its intended audience. A summary of the information to be collected about the data is then outlined, including a template to be used by the consortium partners to describe datasets to be collected and/or produced in the OPEUS project. The application of FAIR data principles to the OPEUS project is discussed, leading into a summary of the data security measures to be followed and the influence of any ethical aspects.

This DMP is a live document which will be updated throughout the project lifetime. A formal update will be released at M30 (April 2019) of the project, as deliverable D9.4 “Data Management Implementation”. This will include more information on aspects such as dataset descriptions (including e.g. references, file formats and metadata), institutional and open access repositories used, whether/how the various data can be reused / shared, and how the data is being preserved.

¹ European Commission Directorate-General for Research & Innovation: “Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020” http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

2. Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronyms	Description
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Document Object Identifier
Dx.x	Deliverable x.x
EC	European Commission
ESSs	Energy Storage Systems
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
H2020	Horizon 2020
Mx	Month x
OC	Open Call
OPEUS	Modelling and strategies for the assessment of OPTimisation of Energy Usage aspects of rail innovation
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
Tx.x	Task x.x
WP	Work Package
Project Participant Short Name:	Project Participant:
UNEW	University of Newcastle upon Tyne (project beneficiary No.1, Project Coordinator)
UIC	International Union of Railways (project beneficiary No.2)
UITP	International Union of Public Transport (project beneficiary No.3)
SAFT	SAFT Technologies (project beneficiary No.4)
UROS	University of Rostock (project beneficiary No.5)
STAV	Stadler Rail Valencia SAU (project beneficiary No.6)

3. Background

This is the deliverable report D9.3 “Data Management Plan” for OPEUS project’s Work Package 9, as required by the project’s Grant Agreement number 730827. It defines the data management processes that will be followed throughout the project’s lifetime. Some of these processes may change or more data types may be collected, which will then be documented in an update of this data management plan as the project evolves. As such, this deliverable is a living document that will be updated and will officially be released to the public as D9.4 “Data Management Implementation” at M30 (i.e. April 2019).

4. Objective/Aim

This deliverable aims to:

- demonstrate compliance with all applicable legislation in relation to the data being collected and used
- report on the data to be collected for use in the delivery of the OPEUS project
- present consortium decisions with respect to making the data FAIR and the respective mechanisms to support these decisions
- discuss the security processes to be applied, including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data
- summarise any related ethical aspects e.g. with respect to (sensitive) personal data, informed consent, etc.

Intended audience

This Data Management Plan (DMP) is for all the researchers within OPEUS and it is considered to be a living document. Being a public document, this Deliverable may also serve as a guide for other researchers working on similar initiatives beyond the specific project.

5. Data Summary

The purpose of the data collection/generation and the relationship of the data to the objectives of the OPEUS project:

The aim of OPEUS is to develop a simulation methodology and accompanying modelling tool to evaluate, improve and optimise the energy consumption of rail systems, with a particular focus on in-vehicle innovation.

The main objectives of OPEUS comprise:

- the definition a simplified but universal energy requirements outlook for European urban rail systems
- the development a comprehensive rail energy usage simulation methodology
- the development of an energy consumption simulation modelling tool for assessment purposes and applicable to urban, regional, high speed and freight duty cycles
- the further assessment of the role and optimisation potential of driver advisory systems (DAS) in relation to control strategies for different representative duty cycles and traction types
- the further assessment of the potential for energy usage optimisation of novel technologies (e.g. next generation ESSs) and strategies (e.g. engine power-off at low loads)
- the provision of a critique of the energy consumption outlook for railway systems.

To do this, three components can be defined within the OPEUS approach:

- the energy simulation model
- the energy use requirements
- the energy usage outlook and optimisation strategies recommendation.

To fulfil its objectives and achieve its aim, OPEUS needs to access, collect, create, process and manage various data types. As the project develops, it may be necessary to involve additional data; this will be included in the next version of this deliverable, D9.4 “Data Management Implementation”, due for completion at M30 (the final month of OPEUS project delivery).

Types of data collected and/or generated:

- *Data from previous EU-funded collaborative projects:*

The OPEUS concept builds upon and extensive range of knowledge and outcomes generated by a number of key EU-funded, collaborative projects including, MERLIN, OSIRIS, CleanER-D, RailEnergy and ModUrbanRoll. The details of their anticipated key inputs to be used are included to the DoA PartB (page 9). OPEUS consortium does not control datasets from these previous projects, but it will exploit them as maybe appropriate to augment the delivery of OPEUS’s project activities.

- *Data provided by / generated by OPEUS consortium partners:*

In delivering an improved simulation tool and testing it within a relevant environment, data from consortium partners will be used e.g. operational data from STAV.

Dataset description:

The following template, below at *Table 1: Dataset Description Template*, will be used to collate information about, and for describing, the datasets that are used and/or produced by the OPEUS project. The compiled descriptions of these datasets will be provided in D9.4 “Data Management Implementation” at M30 (i.e. April 2019):

Table 1: Dataset Description Template

Dataset Reference	OPEUS_WPX_TX.X_vXX: Each dataset will have a reference that will be generated by the combination of the name of the project, the Work Package and Task in which it is generated and its version (for example: OPEUS_WP3_T3.2_v01)
Dataset Name	Name of the dataset
Dataset Description	Each dataset will have a full data description explaining the data provenance, origin and usefulness. Reference may be made to existing data that could be reused.
Standards and metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The metadata attributes list • The used methodologies
File format	All the format that defines data
Data Origin	Specify the origin of the data (including whether created or collected)
Data Size	State the expected size of the data
Data Sharing	Explanation of the sharing policies related to the dataset between the next options: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open: Open for public disposal • Embargo: It will become public when the embargo period applied by the publisher is over. In case it is categorized as embargo the end date of the embargo period must be written in DD/MM/YYYY format. • Restricted: Only for project internal use.
Data Utility	Outline to whom the dataset could be useful – potential secondary users

Archiving and Preservation	The preservation guarantee and the data storage during and after the project (for example: databases, institutional repositories, public repositories, etc.)
Re-used existing data	Yes / No. If “Yes”, state the re-used data and how/from where they were retrieved

Open Access approach:

The OPEUS consortium has agreed to follow an “Open Access” approach (as much as possible depending on the specific data type) following the respective Horizon 2020 guidelines² to ensure that the results of the project results provide the greatest impact possible. OPEUS will ensure the open access³ to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results and will provide access to the research data needed to validate the results presented in deposited scientific publications. Publications and research data made available to third parties will not contain any personal information.

The following lists the minimum fields of metadata that should come with an OPEUS project-generated scientific publication in a repository:

- The terms: “European Union (EU)”, “Horizon 2020”
- Name of the action (Research and Innovation Action)
- Acronym and grant number (OPEUS, 730827)
- Publication date
- Length of embargo period, if applicable
- Persistent identifier

When referencing open access data, OPEUS will include at a minimum the following statement demonstrating EU support (with relevant information being included into the repository metadata):

“The OPEUS project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 730827”.

The OPEUS consortium will strive to make its datasets open access. When this is not the case, the “Data Sharing” element for that particular dataset will describe why access has been restricted.

Regarding specific repositories where OPEUS datasets will be held during and after the project, they will be noted in the “Archiving and Preservation” field of Table 1 (above). In cases where the project partners maintain institutional repositories, these will be listed in OPEUS deliverable D9.4 “Data Management Implementation” at M30 (i.e. April 2019). The project scientific publications

² http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

³ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/open-access_en.htm

and, in some instances, research data will be deposited on the institutional repository depending primarily on the primary creator of the publication and on the data in question. In cases where the project partners do not operate publicly accessible institutional repositories, they will use either a domain specific repository or the EU recommended service OpenAIRE (<http://www.openaire.eu>) as an initial step to finding resources to determine relevant repositories for depositing the scientific publications and the respective data.

The repository will also include information regarding the software, tools and instruments that were used by the dataset creator(s) so that secondary data users can access and then validate the results.

In summary, as a baseline OPEUS partners will deposit:

- Scientific publications – on their respective institute repositories in addition (when relevant) to a public OPEUS repository (such as ZENODO)
- Research data – to the public OPEUS repository collection (when possible)
- Other project output files – to the OPEUS public repository collection (as relevant).

This DMP does not include the actual metadata about the Research Data being produced in OPEUS project. Details about building a repository and accessing this metadata will be provided in deliverable D9.4 “Data Management Implementation” at M30.

6. FAIR Data

OPEUS will in principle participate in the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) but data marked as “Restricted” or under an “Embargo” period will be excluded. To this end, the data that will be generated during and after the project and will be included in ORDP should be ‘FAIR’, that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. These requirements do not affect implementation choices and do not necessarily suggest any specific technology, standard, or implementation solution.

The FAIR principles were generated to improve the practices for data management and data-curation, aiming to describe the principles to be applied to a wide range of data management purposes, whether it is data collection or data management of larger research projects regardless of scientific disciplines.

With the endorsement of the FAIR principles by H2020 and their implementation in the guidelines for H2020, they serve as a template for lifecycle data management and ensure that the most important components for lifecycle are covered. This is intended as an implementation of the FAIR concept rather than a strict technical implementation of the FAIR principles:

- Making data *Findable*, including provisions for metadata:
 - The datasets will have very rich metadata to facilitate the findability
 - All the datasets will have a Digital Object Identifier provided by an OPEUS public repository (e.g., ZENODO)

- The reference used for the dataset will follow the format: OPEUS_WPX_TX.X_vXX, including clear indication of the related WP, activity and version of the dataset
- The standards for metadata will be defined in the “Standards and metadata” section of the dataset description table (see Table 1, above).
- Making data openly *Accessible*:
 - Datasets openly available are marked as “Open” in the “Data Sharing” section of the dataset description table (see Table 1).
 - The repository in which each dataset is stored, including open access datasets, is mentioned in the “Archiving and Preservation” section of the dataset description table (see Table 1)
 - The “Data Sharing” section of the dataset description table (Table 1) will also include information with respect to the methods or software used to access the data of each dataset
 - The data and their associated metadata will be deposited either in a public repository or in an institutional repository
 - The “Data Sharing” section of the dataset description table (see Table 1) will outline the rules to access the data, if restrictions exist.
- Making data *Interoperable*:
 - Metadata vocabularies, standards and methodologies will depend on the repository to be hosted (incl. public, institutional, etc.) and will be provided in the “Standards and metadata” section of the dataset description table (Table 1).
- Making data *Reusable*:
 - All the data producers will license their data if applicable to allow the widest reuse possible. More details about license types and rules will be provided in OPEUS deliverable D9.4 “Data Management Implementation” at M30.
 - The “Data Sharing” section of the dataset description table (see Table 1) is the field where the data sharing policy of each dataset is defined. By default, the data will be made available for reuse. If any constraints exist, an “Embargo” period or “Restricted” flag will be explicitly raised in this section of Table 1.
 - The data producers will make their data available for third-parties within public repositories only for scientific publications validation purposes.

7. Allocation of Resources

In order to face the data management challenges efficiently, all OPEUS partners have to respect the policies set out in this DMP and datasets have to be identified, created, managed and stored appropriately. The OPEUS roles related to the management of the data are:

- The *data controller*, who acts as the point of contact for data protection issues and will coordinate the actions required to liaise between different beneficiaries and their affiliates, as well as their respective data protection agencies, in order to ensure that data collection and processing within the scope of OPEUS, will be carried out according to EU and national legislation. The data controller must ensure that data are shared and easily available
- The *data producer*, which is any entity that produces data within OPEUS's scope. Each data producer is responsible for the integrity and compatibility of its data during the project lifetime. The data producer is responsible for sharing its anonymised datasets through open access repositories, according to the principles and mechanisms defined in the current document. They are in charge of providing the latest version
- The *data manager*, who will coordinate the actions related to data management, will be responsible for the actual implementation of the DMP successive versions and for the compliance to Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) guidelines. As the OPEUS open data will be hosted either by institutional databases or by an open free of charge platform (e.g. ZENODO), no additional costs will be required for hosting the data.

Responsibilities:

UNEW, as project coordinator, is responsible for implementing the DMP.

In principle, all partners are responsible for data generation, metadata production and data quality. Specific responsibilities are to be assigned depending on the data and the internal organisation in the WPs and Tasks where data is created.

Dataset storage and backup, data set archiving and sharing will be, in the majority of cases, the responsibility of the partner(s) who owns the data and/or the servers in which they will be stored.

8. Data Security

Data sharing, storage, backup/recovery and long term data preservation

A “repository” is a mechanism used by a project consortium to make its project results (i.e., publications and scientific data) publicly available and free of charge for any user.

Several options are considered/suggested by the EC in the frame of the Horizon 2020 programme to this aim:

- For depositing scientific publications:
 - Institutional repository of the research institutions
 - Subject-based/thematic repository
 - Centralised repository
- For depositing generated research data:

- A research data repository which allows third parties to access, mine, exploit,
- Reproduce and disseminate free of charge
- Centralised repository

The Consortium is aware of the mandate for open access of publications in the H2020 projects and the participation of the project in the ORDP. The academic institutions participating in OPEUS have available their own repositories which in fact are linked to OpenAIRE. These institutional repositories will be used to deposit the publications generated by them.

A scientific publication and data repository, such as ZENODO (the repository set up by the EC's OpenAIRE initiative in order to unite all the research results arising from EC funded projects), will be used for the sharing and preservation of project outcomes. The Consortium will ensure that scientific results that will not be protected and can be useful for the research community will be duly and timely deposited in the chosen scientific results repository, free of charge to any user.

Considering ZENODO as the repository, the short- and long-term storage of the research data will be secured since they are stored safely in same cloud infrastructure as research data from CERN's Large Hadron Collider. It uses digital preservation strategies to storage multiple online replicas and to back up the files (data files and metadata are backed up on a nightly basis). Therefore, this repository fulfils the main requirements imposed by the EC for data sharing, archiving and preservation of the data generated in OPEUS.

9. Ethical Aspects

There are no ethical issues related to data management in OPEUS, as the project does not handle personal (sensitive) data.

10. Conclusions

This deliverable provides an overview of the data that OPEUS project will produce together with related data processes and requirements that need to be taken into consideration.

The document gives an overview of the anticipated dataset types, defines a set of attributes to be used for describing each dataset, and presents the open access aspects to be followed by the consortium. These include a description, standards, methodologies, sharing and storage methods.

With respect to making the data FAIR and the respective mechanisms to support these decisions are described, with the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects are presented.

This deliverable is a living document which will be updated during the project lifetime as needed, including more detailed information regarding the collected / generated data. The next official updated version will be released as deliverable D9.4 "Data Management Implementation", at M30 (i.e., April 2019), providing more information on such as:

- The descriptions of the different datasets, including their reference, file format, standards, methodologies and metadata and repository to be used
- Institutional repositories in cases where the project partners maintain such a repository
- The use of an appropriate Open Access repository to enable the sharing and reuse of data from the project
- How the data is being curated and will be preserved.